

CULTiVATE

Food Sharing Community of Practice Handbook / D6.4

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Introduction

The Food Sharing Community of Practice (CoP) was developed by 10 Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) and ICLEI Europe within the EU-funded project CULTIVATE. The network has grown into an active space of collaboration and exchange of good practices and has also fostered professional relationships and friendships.

Figure 1: The 10 Food Sharing Initiatives and municipalities that founded the Food Sharing CoP

Food sharing in the CULTIVATE project is defined as “Growing, cooking, eating and redistributing food with others; giving a portion of food to others; using, occupying or enjoying food and food related knowledge, skills, devices and spaces jointly with others.”¹

Food Sharing Initiatives adopt different organisational forms, including co-operatives and social enterprises, charities and for-profits, and they can be led by grassroots, community, private sector or state actors. Examples include seed libraries, community gardens, food related co-operatives, community kitchens, and surplus food redistribution organisations. Municipalities are not FSIs per se, but they were included in the CoP because they can support the set up of new FSIs or the scaling of existing ones in different ways, such as convening, coordination, seed funding, or visibility. Membership in the Food Sharing CoP gives municipalities insights into the work of food sharing initiatives, their challenges and opportunities, and potential actions that could support them in terms of policies, regulations, finances and logistics.

¹ See also the Food Sharing Dictionary: https://cultivate-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/CTV_food-sharing-dictionary_compressed.pdf

FSIs and other CULTIVATE partners have collectively developed the following definition of the Food Sharing CoP:

We are a Community of Practice of organisations and people that work on or have an interest in food sharing. We are bound by the desire to create a sustainable and just food system, a drive to act and take concrete actions in our communities, and an urgency for change. We believe that the current mainstream food system is damaging people and the planet, and food sharing can support the creation of alternative food systems that are transformative, socially just and circular.

The goals of the Food Sharing Community of Practice are to:

- Share knowledge, experiences and good practices about running or contributing to food sharing initiatives
- Provide inspiration about what is possible in food sharing
- Create a network of people working in the same area (topically or geographically) and facing similar challenges
- Push food sharing and alternative food systems at the top of the public agenda by coordinating our advocacy efforts at local, national and EU levels

These goals align with the generally accepted definition of CoPs: a Community of Practice is a group of people who care about the same issues or face similar problems and who meet regularly to learn from each other and improve what they do. Drawing on the work of Lave and Wenger (1991) and Wenger (1998),² it is usually described as having three key elements: a shared topic or domain of concern, a community based on mutual engagement and support, and a common practice made up of shared tools, experiences, and ways of working.

Membership to the Food Sharing CoP is open to active food sharing initiatives, people and groups that are thinking about starting a food sharing initiative, as well as people and institutions (including municipalities) that want to support food sharing. Members should be eager to share their experiences and interact with others, both online and at in-person meetings.

This document is meant for all current and prospective members of the Food Sharing Community of Practice, whether they are part of food sharing initiatives or they want to research, support or fund food sharing. It describes the steps that brought the Food Sharing CoP to life and its current structure and governance. It concludes with concrete lessons learned on how to set up and manage a European Food Sharing Community of Practice.

² Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge University Press. Wenger, E. (1998). *Communities of Practice. Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511803932>

The growth of the Food Sharing CoP

The CULTIVATE Community of Practice (CoP) grew step by step over the course of four years. The aim was to help Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) get to know each other, build stronger links between groups working on similar issues, and share practical, context-specific knowledge and skills.

Phase 1: Online webinars

In the first year of the project, eleven online webinars were organised to lay the groundwork for the Community of Practice. All sessions took place online, were recorded, and made available on the CULTIVATE website for later use.³

Each webinar followed the same interactive format. Two food sharing initiatives presented their work, experiences, and ways of dealing with a specific theme. After the presentations, there was a facilitated group discussion. The presenting initiative shared a concrete challenge they were facing, and other initiatives could respond with ideas, advice, and possible solutions.

Across the series, four key dimensions of the CoP became visible:

- **Community:** building trust, relationships, and a sense of belonging.
- **Practice:** exchanging tools, solutions, and practical ways of working.
- **Learning:** strengthening skills, reflection, and capacities.
- **Advocacy:** shaping narratives, influencing policy, and supporting scaling efforts.

Webinar Theme	FSI Involved	Contribution to CoP
1. The Why: Why do we save & share food?	Boroume and Zusammen Leben	Framed food sharing beyond redistribution of surplus food to include other practices such as working with farmers.
2. Multifunctionality of Food Sharing and Saving	Espigoladors and Upfarming	Highlighted the multifunctionality of food sharing, expanding the sCoPe of activities to include educational activities, for-profit production, logistics and advocacy.
3. Equality in Food Sharing and Saving	Nesehnutí	Addressed inclusion, access, and co-creation with marginalised groups.
4. Spaces of Conviviality	Zusammen Leben and Upfarming	Showed importance of physical/social spaces for community building and participation.
5. Involving Volunteers	FoodCloud and Boroume	Explored volunteer engagement, retention, and corporate volunteering.
6. Regulatory Challenges in Food Sharing and Saving	Espigoladors and Milan Food Waste Hubs	Highlighted need for enabling policies, co-created regulation, and governance models.
7. Finance and Funding for FSIs	Brighton & Hove Food Partnership and City of Utrecht	Showed diversified funding models, hybrid finance, and role of municipalities in supporting food sharing practices.

³ Available at <https://cultivate-project.eu/resources/>

8. Technical and Digital Solutions	Terra Pagesa and FoodCloud	Presented digital platforms, logistics solutions, and traceability tools for food distribution and redistribution.
9. Approaching Stakeholders in the Local Food System	City of Utrecht and Terra Pagesa	Focused on multi-stakeholder engagement, governance structures, and coordination of food sharing across partners and networks.
10. Communicating with Audiences	Brighton & Hove Food Partnership and Nesehnutí	Explored outreach strategies, storytelling, advocacy, and engaging new audiences.
11. Scaling Up Food Sharing Initiatives	Milan Food Waste Hubs and FoodCloud	Addressed replication, scaling strategies, and infrastructure challenges for food surplus redistribution.

Table 1: Food Sharing Webinars - Themes and contribution to the CoP

Phase 2: Buddy Programme

Based on the relationships and themes that emerged in the webinars, the CoP then moved into a second phase: an in-person Buddy Programme. This took place between March and June 2024 and focused on deepening peer learning.

Figure 2: The buddy visit in Athens included hands-on food saving. Credits: Boroume

The Buddy Programme consisted of bilateral site visits between FSIs. Selected initiatives hosted and visited each other to get first-hand insight into how their partners work, the local context they operate in, and how they address common challenges identified earlier in the webinars. In total, ten buddy visits were organised.

The pairings were set up using clear criteria:

- A shared challenge that had already come up in the webinars.
- Potential for collaboration beyond the project.
- Diversity of contexts and food sharing models.

Buddy 1	Buddy 2	Focus Topic
Utrecht Foodcloud	Upfarming Espigoladores	<i>Designing spaces and including communities</i>
Terra Pagesa	Boroume	<i>Dealing with different amounts of food waste and integrating the whole supply chain</i>
Milan	Brighton & Hove Food Partnership	<i>Working with local stakeholders and integrating the whole supply chain</i>
Zusammen Leben	Nesehnuti	<i>Combining logistics and distribution efforts with culture and education</i>
		<i>Handling many different projects at once and still finding time to advocate for one’s cause</i>

Table 2: Buddy visits participants and focus topic

Each buddy visit was hands-on. It usually included:

- Visits to key places such as community kitchens, gardens, or food distribution centres.
- Direct interaction with staff, volunteers, and local stakeholders.
- A dedicated workshop session focusing on a shared challenge (using methods such as the “Crazy Eights” exercise).⁴

Many FSIs described the buddy visits as one of the most valuable parts of the CoP. Visiting each other in person helped deepen relationships and gave a much clearer understanding of how other initiatives work in their own context. Having dedicated time to visit, explore ideas, and talk in depth made it possible to really develop these relationships and find inspiration. One member explains: “Really good stuff from the webinars, but where we've met on the buddy level, we connected, we spent a couple of days together and that relationship is much stronger. Whereas for some of the other FSIs, other than a couple of presentations here and there, I haven't really got my head around what they're doing and I feel [I lacked] that richness you only really get it from visiting and seeing it and you can kind of have those conversations”.

Phase 3: Bootcamp and Action Plans

After the webinars and buddy visits, the CoP entered a third phase focused on bringing together what had been learned and apply it to each FSI's context. This took place in a three-day in-person Bootcamp in Lisbon in June 2024.

The main goal of the Bootcamp was to help initiatives reflect systematically on the insights gained during the webinars and buddy visits. During the Bootcamp, they assessed their own organisational strengths and challenges and worked on concrete “Action Plans” to strengthen or expand their activities in their local contexts.

These Action Plans were designed as practical roadmaps to scale or deepen innovations within each FSI. They also sparked exchanges between initiatives working on similar themes, such as:

- **Edible neighbourhoods:** Utrecht and Brighton & Hove Food Partnership
- **Cooking and community engagement:** Boroume and Nesehnutí
- **Working with farmers:** FoodCloud and Terra Pagesa
- **Organisational change:** Upfarming and Zusammen Leben
- **Engagement with policymakers:** Espigoladors and Milan Food Waste Hubs

FSIs described the Action Plans as one of the CoP elements that led to the strongest organisational change, because they turned shared learning into clear next steps. The Action Plans and the resources associated with them allowed FSIs to experiment. In the words of one member: “This is an enormous luxury, to have money available to create something that you wanted to create. This

Figure 3: Group work during the CULTIVATE Bootcamp, June 2024.
Credits: Ana Sofia Carvalho

⁴ Crazy Eights is a brainstorming exercise that aims to develop and sketch eight innovative solutions to a problem under/within eight minutes.

is an exceptional opportunity for an NGO. This is precisely what we did. I mean, we took advantage of it. We used that to fulfil one of our past dreams, and we are fortunate to have been able to try it out. I do not know if we continue. It looks difficult because it turns out to be a bit too expensive for Greek companies. You know what the big difference is? You know how the saying goes. You don't know it unless you try it. So, unless we had tried this out, it would always be only a dream. We could have done it. No, now we know. And the only reason we know is that we had the resources to try it.”

Food Sharing Initiative	Action Plan Innovation	Main Activities
Brighton and Hove Food Partnership	Developing “Edible Brighton”, a campaign creating edible landscapes in deprived areas, inspired by Utrecht’s edible neighbourhood.	Co-designed activities of the Edible Brighton campaign with residents and city council; 2 pilot Food Forests; training 15 Edible Leaders (food forest managers); developed a blueprint for city-wide “Right to Grow” strategy.
FoodCloud	Extending an existing app-enabled approach to redistribution to allow farmers to redistribute surplus directly to community partners.	Adapted and tested the Foodiverse app for farmers, recruited and trained 2 growers and 22 new community partners, to facilitate direct surplus food donations of over 50 tonnes of fresh vegetables. Collected feedback, refined the model, and promoted learning through events and reports.
Boroume	Developing corporate food-saving seminars to expand volunteering and anti-food waste education.	Set up hands-on food-saving workshops as corporate volunteering, training 165 people; used funds from corporate volunteering to organise 8 cooking workshops for charity cooks; food prepared donated locally.
Espigoladors	Building and rolling out gleaning awareness workshops to scale sustainable harvest recovery and policy advocacy.	Conducted eight Gleaning Awareness workshops in separate regions in Spain; mentored 4 new gleaning groups; created toolbox for replication of gleaning activities; policy advocacy for gleaning to be included in Food Waste Law.
Terra Pagesa	Developing digital and commercial innovation for short food supply chains, improving logistics and B2B catering sales.	Optimised warehouse software; developed a last-mile logistics service; created a sales strategy for schools and hospitals; changed business model, connecting over 5000 farmers with around 50 clients (local shops, collective catering, etc).
Upfarming	Developing new communications strategy for improved urban food and climate literacy.	Developed new business and communications model; rebranding and outreach campaign; improved design of website and materials.
City of Milan	Developing and testing of CARE – Cargobike Action for Rescuing Edibles, a low-emission logistics model for food redistribution.	Co-designed CARE strategy with local partners; piloted cargo-bike recovery routes from schools, recovering 3 metric tons of surplus food from 18 schools amounting to approximately 1500 redistributed meals.
Municipality of Utrecht	Expanding shared maintenance of the Edible Neighbourhood Rijnvliet – embedding community stewardship in city policy.	Co-created maintenance plan with residents and city officials for the edible neighbourhood; created a short film on the vision ⁵ for the edible neighbourhood as an introduction to residents on how to engage with the plants (only picking, maintenance done by municipality); established new community meeting spaces in the neighbourhood.
Zusammen Leben	Participatory community transformation through food, inclusion and climate action.	Established a clearer organisational structure through a new organigram; improved financial systems and strategy; developed a “new generation” approach to attract, involve, and retain young people.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4UaUY-G-kF4>

Nesehnutí	Expansion of community cooking activities to connect refugees and locals	Development of “buddy cooking” activity, pairing experienced chefs with newcomer amateur chefs; developed structured communication and event planning strategy; organised 9 community events and 12 public events.
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Table 3: FSI Action Plans - Aimed innovation and main activities

Figure 4: A gleaning initiative organised by Espigoladores. Credits: Leonardo Improta.

Phase 4: Coaching, expanding the network and consolidating the CoP

The fourth phase of the CoP development focuses on peer-peer coaching. In this phase, CULTIVATE food sharing initiatives worked with actors beyond the original project partners to widen the Community of Practice. The FSIs found organisations and individuals who were either already running food sharing projects or were interested in starting one. They offered them training and advice derived from both their learnings from CULTIVATE and their day-to-day experience. CULTIVATE FSIs could choose their preferred mode of delivering the coaching, whether online or in person: some organised one-to-one trainings, other organised group site visits and workshops, and others a three-day event following the methodology of the Bootcamp. The participants were then invited to join the Community of Practice by signing up to the digital platform hosted on Sustainable

Food Systems Network, explained in the next section. This was fundamental to achieve the project's goal of 100+ members of the CoP by the end of the project.

Therefore, the goal of the coaching sessions was twofold:

1. To share and transfer the methods, tools, and experiences developed during CULTIVATE (e.g. sharing knowledge about the suite of Compass tools, as well as knowledge developed from webinars, buddy visits, bootcamp, and local Action Plan development and implementation);
2. To enlarge and strengthen the CoP, by enrolling new members and creating long-term collaboration channels.

Alongside the coaching sessions, the CoP coordinators initiated a co-design process with the original CoP members and consortium members to consolidate the CoP. The process focused on understanding what they appreciated in the CoP and what could be improved, as well as their vision for the future of the CoP. This included how to include newcomers from the coaching sessions and to communicate and coordinate within a much larger network. Coaching activities aimed to bring new initiatives into an already well-established network of FSIs. This added a new layer to the CoP: supporting newcomers while maintaining strong ties among existing members. Another result of the co-design process was that the CoP should be open to anyone interested in learning about and supporting food sharing, not only FSIs.

The goal of the consolidation was to create a space that would function as a repository of resources, templates and knowledge, as well as establish a platform for exchange and knowledge sharing that would be:

- **Informative:** contains resources, templates, events info
- **Collaborative:** members can contribute with posts, events, files
- **Connecting:** allows contact with other members (in compliance with GDPR)
- **Easy:** both easy to use *and* easy to set up and manage

Creating a subgroup named Food Sharing Community of Practice on the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) platform met all these criteria and was therefore selected as the preferred option. Details of this platform are elaborated in the next section.

The Food Sharing CoP Platform

The digital platform of the Food Sharing CoP

To accommodate the arrival of new members and move away from only communicating through email and whatsapp, the Food Sharing CoP coordination team explored different options. After careful consideration and feedback from the rest of the Consortium, the best option was found to be creating a sub-group on the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) platform. SFSN facilitates communication and collaboration amongst stakeholders in sustainable food systems (SFS) across the globe. Their platform enables other groups to create a space with the same features, but that can be fully independently managed and moderated.

The platform includes many useful features for building and managing a CoP (see Figure 5):

- Members can post different types of inputs (such as personal introductions, success stories, reflections) on a feed that is visible to all members.
- Members can search and contact other members in the repository, using filters to find the exact type of people they are looking for (e.g. filtering by country, type of food sharing activity, type of involvement in food sharing).
- Members can share upcoming events with others.
- Members can upload useful resources (documents, templates, videos) to share with the rest of the CoP.

Figure 5: The landing page of the Food Sharing CoP platform on SFSN

Governance of the Food Sharing CoP Platform

The platform is managed by the Community of Practice coordinators (currently ICLEI Europe) in collaboration with one FSI or academic member (FSI/academic manager) on a rotating basis, changing every two months.

The tasks for the CoP coordinators include:

- **Accept new members**
CoP coordinators receive an email (to a shared email address) when new members sign up, they review the application and accept or decline it. The platform automatically sends a welcome e-mail to new members.
- **Prompt members to contribute to the platform**
The CoP Platform is a lively and dynamic place thanks to contributions from its members. The CoP coordinators send reminders to members engage with the platform. The minimum contribution expected from members is to introduce themselves once they join the platform, so that other members can already learn a little more about them. Beyond these introductions, contributions can be:
 - posting an upcoming event in the calendar page
 - writing a post to report about an event that happened, or sharing an interesting article/blog/book
 - uploading a resource (document, video, infographic, report, etc)
 - repost something from another social media platform (e.g. LinkedIn, Instagram)
- **Ensure posts and files uploaded by members align with guidelines**
CoP coordinators ensure that posts and resources uploaded by members comply with community guidelines.
- **Respond to questions members may have about the CoP and the platform**
Information on the CoP and the platform (e.g. how it functions, how it's governed, what can or cannot be shared) is available in a post pinned in the feed of the CoP platform. However, in case members still have questions, they can address them to the CoP coordinators by contacting them through their platform or at the email address foodsharingcopmanagers-europe@iclei.org.
- **Send newsletter with CoP updates**
CoP coordinators use the newsletter function of SFSN and a template to share with all members some of the highlights from the past month. This includes, for example, recently added members, interesting posts and upcoming events.

The tasks of the rotating FSI/academic managers include:

- **Introduce a thematic strand for a sub-group**
FSI/academic managers choose a topic based on their activity (e.g. gleaning, communal cooking, urban gardens) or a challenge they are encountering (e.g. securing funding, engaging volunteers, accessing long-term spaces) or their country of activity. This topic will form the basis for a sub-group inside the Community of Practice, which other interested members can engage with.
- **Organise monthly thematic meet-up**
FSI/academic managers organise regular meetings for members interested in the thematic strand of their choice. These meet-ups do not need to have a structured agenda and a fixed format, but can simply be moments when CoP members come together to exchange and talk about the topic. The FSI/academic managers have to create a link on a conference platform (e.g. Teams, Zoom, Google Meets, etc) and add the event in the CoP Platform calendar.

Once their role as FSI/academic manager passes to another member, the FSI that started the thematic strand can either continue to organise regular meetings on their topic or pass the organisational baton to the next FSI/academic manager.

- **Set up a thematic folder in the Resources page**

If it does not exist yet, the FSI manager creates a new folder in the “Resources” page to upload documents and inputs on the topic, as well as meeting notes of the monthly meet up.

Lessons learned

After four years of setting up, managing and living the CoP, both coordinators and members have come up with a list of lessons learned on how to create a vibrant Community of Practice of Food Sharing Initiatives and Supporters.

1. Build on shared challenges and values, not just activities

- Start from the problems everyone recognises: lack of funding, overworked teams, volunteer retention, dealing with food waste logistics, etc.
 - Use these shared struggles to create solidarity and trust (“we are all dealing with this”), not only to exchange tips.
 - Name the common values openly: food justice, social inclusion, climate responsibility, and a “doer” mentality.
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2. Combine structured activities with space for informal connection

- Design clear, recurring formats (webinars, peer visits, bootcamps, online workshops) so people know what to expect.
 - In each format, mix structure and openness: presentations, then small-group discussion around a real challenge from one initiative, then time for informal conversation.
 - Encourage follow-up beyond events: peer-to-peer calls, extra site visits, small joint experiments, even simple gestures like sending products or materials to each other.
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3. Use both online and in-person formats – for different purposes

- Use **online** sessions to:
 - Start relationships and map who does what.
 - Maintain the network between in-person meetings through regular, purposeful calls.
 - Use **in-person** meetings to:
 - Deepen trust, by including social time (shared meals, walks, informal talks).
 - Allow “embodied learning”: seeing kitchens, gardens, warehouses, neighbourhoods and volunteers in action.
 - Plan them as complementary: without online continuity, the CoP loses momentum; without in-person contact, trust and depth remain limited.
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4. Embrace diversity but create good matches

- Recognise that people find it easier to relate to those with similar roles (e.g. municipalities with municipalities, grassroots with grassroots).
- When planning buddy visits or small groups, use matching criteria such as:
 - Similar challenges.
 - Potential for collaboration beyond the project.

- Some overlap in context or role.

At the same time, keep spaces where very different actors meet; municipalities can learn from food sharing initiatives based in other cities about policies and activities that other municipalities are undertaking, and challenges that FSIs in their own constituency could potentially face. This can trigger deeper learning, precisely because power relations are more neutral than in day-to-day work.

5. Plan for turnover and changing participants

- Expect that people will move jobs or have shifting workloads and keep basic documentation accessible (notes, recordings, short summaries, contact lists) so newcomers can catch up quickly.
 - When a new person joins from an existing member organisation, nudge them to reach out to existing members to help them integrate.
-

6. Treat the CoP as a shared toolbox, not a top-down training

- Focus on concrete methods and tools members can adapt: co-design exercises, volunteer models, gleaning practices, income-generation ideas like corporate volunteering.
 - Capture these in simple, reusable formats (one-page descriptions, checklists, templates, short videos) so people can return to them when timing and context are right.
 - Encourage adaptation, not Copying: “What part of this could work in your context?” rather than “Who can implement this exactly as is?”
-

7. Strengthen FSI members’ position in local governance, not just their practices

- Help food sharing initiatives see themselves as part of a wider field of food system change, not isolated projects.
- Support exchange between FSI members and municipality members to trigger learning on local food systems governance.
- Give them language and examples they can use when talking with municipalities, funders, and partners.
- Use the network to increase their confidence: “Others are doing this too; we are part of a broader movement.”
- Accept that the CoP rarely changes policy directly; instead, it builds the relationships and confidence that make future engagement more effective.